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About the project

Green Hive is a Cooperation Partnership in Vocational Education and Training (VET), co-funded by the **Erasmus+ Programme of the EU**. The project, implemented by the Technological University of the Shannon: Midlands Midwest (Ireland), Lascò (Italy), KEAN (Greece), Femxa (Spain) and Team 4 Excellence (Romania), aims to develop a **European platform-based Ecosystem for Sustainability Education**.

Would you like to learn more? Reach out to us anytime via the project website greenhiveproject.eu if you have any questions or would like more information.

GREEN HIVE KNOWLEDGE CAFÉ

»»» 19TH OF JUNE 2025

The third **Green Hive Knowledge Café** took place online, hosted by **Team4Excellence**. The event aimed to enhance knowledge exchange on strengthening sustainability education and to foster cross-border collaboration among VET providers across Europe. Educators and learners from different countries came together in this virtual café to discuss how we can integrate green skills into vocational training and work together on real-world challenges.

During the session, participants explored Green Hive's approach to embedding sustainability competences in VET curricula, were introduced to the **European Contest "Sustainability – New Perspectives for a Wicked Problem"** and previewed our **Community Platform** – a new digital hub for resources, collaboration, and contest participation. They also engaged in peer-to-peer discussions to share project ideas, reflect on potential partnerships, and reinforce their roles as sustainability changemakers in their communities. By connecting people across borders, the event exemplified Green Hive's core mission: empowering individuals and organisations with innovative, inclusive training solutions for sustainability.

NEW PERSPECTIVES FOR A WICKED PROBLEM” – RESULTS & WINNERS

We are thrilled to announce the results of our European Contest for Green Combs, “Sustainability – New Perspectives for a Wicked Problem.” This competition showcased the creativity, collaboration, and commitment of VET learners and educators across Europe in tackling urgent sustainability challenges. Teams from our Green Combs submitted short videos proposing innovative solutions to pressing issues – from rethinking waste and reducing energy consumption to ensuring inclusive green transitions and protecting water resources. After many inspiring contributions from all five partner countries, one project stood out above the rest.

Liceul Tehnologic “Lazăr Edeleanu” from Năvodari, Romania has been crowned the contest winner with their project **“Fighting for Wellness”**. Their submission impressed the jury with its creativity, relevance, and strong commitment to promoting sustainability and community engagement

WHAT'S NEXT?

»»» Sustainability: New Perspectives for a Wicked Problem

The winning team is invited to present their solution at the Green Hive **Final Conference**, giving them the chance to showcase their idea on a European stage. Their project will also be featured in our upcoming **e-publication Sustainability: New Approaches for a Wicked Problem**, ensuring their innovative work gains broad visibility and impact.

While our champions prepare to share their success on the big stage, we celebrate every participant as a changemaker – each team's effort has contributed to our shared mission of advancing sustainability through education. This outcome exemplifies Green Hive's goals of **empowering educators and learners** with new ways to foster **sustainability competences** across Europe.

STAY TUNED! Sustainability: New Approaches for a Wicked Problem (our contest results e-publication) will be released soon. It will be widely promoted by the project consortium at national and European levels, providing a platform to inspire others with the creative solutions developed by our Green Combs.

Would you like to learn more?

Visit our website for the latest news, resources, and opportunities to get involved.

[CLICK HERE](#)

